

**LEARNING STYLES, MOTIVATION, AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF
GRADE IV LEARNERS: A STUDY IN PANGANTUCAN
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Learning Styles, Motivation, and Academic Achievement of Grade IV Learners: A Study in Pangantucan North District

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Abstract

This study was generally conducted to determine the learning styles, motivation and academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan of the Grade IV pupils in the Pangantucan North District, Division of Bukidnon for the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study aimed to: determine the learning styles preference of student in terms of: a. visual, b. auditory and c. kinaesthetic; determine the level of motivation of the pupils in terms of: a. Interest; b. Perceived Competence; c. Effort; and d. Pressure; to assess the academic achievement of Grade VI pupils and to analyze the significant relationship among the academic achievement, motivation and learning style of the pupils. The data were gathered from 137 Grade IV pupils of Pangantucan North District with different learning style preference, level of motivation and academic achievement. This research study was a descriptive-correlational type of research. Primarily, it involved gathering of data to test the hypotheses. A survey questionnaire was used as the primary instrument in recording the response of the respondents' learning style and motivation. The records of the academic achievement of the pupils were taken from the teacher of the grade four pupils of Pangantucan North District, Pangantucan, Bukidnon. Descriptive statistics was used to describe the Academic Achievement of the Grade IV learners. Mean and standard deviation was used to determine the preferred learning style and motivation of the Grade IV Learners while Pearson r was used to determine the relationship between the learning style, motivation and the academic achievement of the Grade IV pupils. Findings revealed that the learning style of the majority of Grade IV Learners is Visual learners while others were auditory learners and then kinesthetic learners. Effort is their highest motivation followed by interest, perceived competence and pressure. Their academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan is satisfactory and that there is no significant relationship between pupils' academic achievement, learning styles and motivation. Therefore, the null hypotheses were accepted.

Keywords: *learning style, motivation, academic achievement*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has completely destroyed all social domains, including education. This has resulted in temporary school closures, an increase in online and distant learning, and home confinement, all of which have negatively impacted the lives of children, teachers, and parents worldwide (Zaccoletti, Sonia, et al., 2020). It has significantly transformed daily life by introducing unparalleled sanitary, political, economic, social, and educational problems. All of these issues have had a significant impact on educational systems worldwide. The transition to online learning has presented obstacles for teachers, learners, and parents, necessitating immediate adaptation and resilience. The swift alteration in instructional delivery methods and an unpredictable future may impede learners' academic motivation.

Moreover, we acknowledge that school and home are distinct contexts that require kids to assume different roles. In this scenario, learners have experienced a lack of physical interaction with both their teachers and peers. Nevertheless, the learning persists. Achievement is an intangible aspiration for individuals. However, the path to academic success is arduous, protracted, and constrained. A multitude of factors influence the academic performance and achievement of learners.

The Pangantucan North District has implemented blended learning, incorporating modular learning modalities as well as synchronous and asynchronous learning across all schools in the district. This is a novel approach not only for the teachers, but also for all those within the Department of Education. Education is an ongoing process, and it is everyone's responsibility to ensure that all school-aged children continue their studies.

Learning style denotes an individual's favored method of assimilating new knowledge for effective learning. It pertains to the manner in which learners acquire knowledge rather than the content of that knowledge. The theory of experiential learning asserts that learning is the process of generating knowledge through the transformation of experience. The basic objective of teaching is to facilitate the learning process. This process considers understanding learners' learning behavior as an integral component. The learning process varies among individuals; even within the same educational setting, learners do not acquire knowledge at the same levels or qualities. Research indicates that individuals employ varied methodologies in the learning process, and no singular strategy can ensure optimal learning conditions for everyone. This may pertain to learners' diverse backgrounds, strengths, weaknesses, interests, aspirations, motivation levels, and study methodologies. To enhance undergraduate education, teachers must increase their awareness of these many methodologies. Learning styles can assist learners and teachers in enhancing their learning and teaching methodologies, respectively.

Motivation serves as a stimulus for human conduct. Environmental factors and individual traits influence and limit motivation, as this

definition emphasizes. Over the last forty years, experts have sought to comprehend how motivation improves learners' learning and academic performance. Academic motivation refers to learners' ideas, objectives, and values that influence the academic or school-related tasks they choose to do and persist in. Wentzel and Wigfield (2019).

This study aims to identify learners' preferred learning styles, their level of motivation, and the relationship between these factors and their academic achievement. The researcher seeks to explore how understanding learners' learning styles and motivation levels can assist teachers in evaluating and enhancing various activities and teaching strategies. When applied systematically, these insights can help address and reduce learners' underperformance.

Research Questions

Generally, this study attempted to determine the learning styles, motivation, and their effects on the academic achievement of the grade IV learners of the Pangantucan North district for the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learning style preference of learners in terms of a. visual, b. auditory and c. kinesthetic?
2. What is the level of motivation of the learners in terms of a. interest; b. Perceived Competence; c. Effort; and d. Pressure?
3. What is the academic achievement of Grade IV learners?
4. Is there a significant relationship between academic achievement, motivation and learning style of the learners?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. It quantitatively and qualitatively described the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The data collected were utilized to test the hypothesis and address questions about the current status of the subjects under investigation. Additionally, the study was correlational as it aimed to determine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Specifically, it examined the learning styles and motivation that significantly influence the academic achievement of Grade IV learners.

Respondents

The researcher utilized purposive sampling by including the entire population of Grade IV learners in the Pangantucan North District. The respondents of the study comprised 137 Grade IV learners, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by School*

Schools	No. of Learners	No. of Respondents
Portulin ES	25	25
Mendis ES	24	24
Sinasaan ES	20	20
New Eden ES	18	18
San Miguel ES	24	24
Concepcion ES	16	16
San Vicente ES	10	10
Total	137	137

Instrument

The researcher utilized questionnaires to assess the psycho-social attributes of the respondents. The Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (IMI), a multidimensional tool designed to evaluate participants' subjective experiences related to specific activities, was used to measure intrinsic motivation. Additionally, the Learning Style Inventory (LSI) was employed to identify the learners' preferred learning styles. The LSI consisted of 20 question statements requiring personal evaluations based on various situations.

Data Analysis

To answer Problem 1, descriptive statistics, specifically frequencies and percentages, were used to determine the learning style preferences of the learners in terms of visual, auditory, and kinesthetic modalities.

To address Problem 2, the mean and standard deviation were utilized to evaluate the level of motivation of the learners in terms of interest, perceived competence, effort, and pressure.

To answer Problem 3, frequencies and percentages were applied to analyze the academic achievement of the Grade IV learners based on their grades.

To address Problem 4, the F-test (ANOVA) was employed to determine if there is a significant relationship between the learners' academic achievement, motivation, and learning styles. This statistical test assessed the interrelationships among the variables under study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data collected from the questionnaires to identify the learning styles, levels of motivation, and their impact on the academic achievement of Grade IV learners in the Pangantucan North District, Division of Bukidnon, for the school year 2022-2023. It also examines the significant relationships between learning styles, motivation, and the academic performance of the learners.

The discussion of findings primarily focuses on the learning styles, motivation, and academic achievement of Grade IV learners in Araling Panlipunan. The presentation follows the sequence of the research questions outlined in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Learning Style Preference of Grade IV Learners

The Learning styles namely visual, auditory, and kinesthetic of the one hundred thirty-seven (137) Grade IV elementary learners of Pangantucan North District, Division of Bukidnon for the S.Y 2022-2023 are presented in Tables 2, 3, and 4.

Table 2 presents the visual learning style Preference of Grade IV Learners.

Table 2. Learning styles preference of learners in terms of visuals

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Understand what some say through Charts, diagrams, and maps.	4.30	1.032	A	Very True of Me
2.	need written directions for tasks.	4.25	1.083	A	Very True of Me
3.	understand discussions better when the teacher writes on the board.	4.23	1.125	A	Very True of Me
4.	remember something better if I write it down.	4.15	1.148	O	Generally True of Me
5.	use color-coding to help me as I learn or work.	3.91	1.322	O	Generally True of Me
6.	remember people's faces but not their names.	3.83	1.281	O	Generally True of Me
7.	prefer to learn with TV or video rather than other media.	3.83	1.309	O	Generally True of Me
8.	take detailed notes during class discussions.	3.68	1.474	O	Generally True of Me
9.	listen, and visualize pictures, numbers, or words in my head.	3.47	1.471	O	Generally True of Me
10.	have to look at people to understand what they say.	3.37	1.558	O	Generally True of Me
	Overall	3.90	.463	O	Generally True of Me

Legend: 4.20-5.00 = Always (A) / Very true of me | 3.20-4.19 = Often (O) / Generally true of me | 2.60-3.19 = Sometimes (S) / Moderately true of me | 1.80-2.59 = Rarely (R) / Slightly true of me | 1.00-1.79 = Never (N) / Not at all true of me

Table 2 shows reveals that the statements “Understand what someone says through Charts, diagrams, and maps” has a mean = 4.30, sd = 1.032 with a descriptive rating of Always (A) and qualitative interpretation of Very True of Me; “need written directions for tasks” has a mean = 4.25, sd = 1.083 with the descriptive rating of Always (A) and qualitative interpretation of Very True of Me; “understand discussions better when the teacher writes on the board” with the mean = 4.23, sd = 1.125 with the descriptive rating of Always (A) and qualitative interpretation of Very True of Me. Other statements were generally true of them. The statement “have to look at people to understand what they say” has the mean = 3.37, SD = 1.558 with the descriptive rating of often(O) and qualitative interpretation of Generally True of Me had the lowest mean. Overall, the statements on the learning style preference of learners in terms of visuals were generally true of the learner with the mean = 3.90, SD = .463 with the descriptive rating of often(O) and qualitative interpretation of Generally True of Me.

This indicates that their score reflects a preference for a learning method that fosters motivation to learn and to read. They desire a tangible representation to facilitate visualization and comprehension. Recognizing that kids have diverse learning styles, teachers must devise strategies to engage and inspire all learners in their learning and reading endeavors. As emphasized by Haggart (2012) Visual learners favor acquiring knowledge through observation and demonstrations. Visual learners typically engage in quiet yet focused study when learning. They frequently engaged in doodling while listening (Smith, 2016). Highlighting, graph creation, and illustration are among their favored learning activities (Fleming, 2019). Visual learners typically process information through imagery, thinking in pictures and visualizing with precision.

The visual learning style, sometimes known as the spatial learning style, involves the association of knowledge with visuals. This learning technique necessitates that learners initially observe the knowledge they are expected to acquire. Individuals with a visual learning style are commonly designated as visual-spatial learners. It is a challenge for teachers to fulfill the expectations of visual learners by providing diverse instructional resources that facilitate immediate and effective learning.

Table 3 shows the auditory learning style preference of the Grade IV learners.

Table 3 shows that the statement “remember things better if I discuss them with someone” has a mean of 4.23, SD = 1.100 was very true of the learners. Seven statements in the table were generally true of the learners. The statement “easily remember jokes that I hear” has a mean of 3.18, SD = 1.548, and “like to listen to music when I study or work” has a mean of 3.09, SD = 1.736) which was moderately true of them. Overall, the statements on learning styles preferred by learners in terms of auditory were generally true of the

learners has a mean of 3.58, $SD = .87$ with the descriptive rating of often(O) and qualitative interpretation of Generally True of Me.

Table 3. *Learning style preference of learners in terms of auditory*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation	Interpretation
1. remember things better if I discuss them with someone.	4.23	1.100	A	Very True of Me
2. prefers to learn by listening to a class discussion than reading.	4.06	1.293	O	Generally True of Me
3. needs oral directions for a task.	3.82	1.514	O	Generally True of Me
4. remembers peoples' names but not their faces.	3.61	1.400	O	Generally True of Me
5. can identify people by their voices (e.g., on the phone).	3.56	1.444	O	Generally True of Me
6. Listen to the sound more than I watch the screen, When I turn on the TV.	3.51	1.383	O	Generally True of Me
7. Can think with the help of Background sound	3.45	1.465	O	Generally True of Me
8. can understand what people say even when I cannot see them.	3.24	1.488	O	Generally True of Me
9. easily remembers jokes that I hear.	3.18	1.548	S	Moderately True of Me
10. likes to listen to music when I study or work.	3.09	1.736	S	Moderately True of Me
Overall	3.58	.874	O	Generally True of Me

Legend: 4.20-5.00 = Always (A) / Very true of me | 3.20-4.19 = Often (O) / Generally true of me | 2.60-3.19 = Sometimes (S) / Moderately true of me | 1.80-2.59 = Rarely (R) / Slightly true of me | 1.00-1.79 = Never (N) / Not at all true of me

This suggests that auditory learners prefer listening to discussions as a means to gain inspiration and acquire knowledge. They rely on hearing and listening to others' spoken instructions to enhance their learning (Haggart, 2002). As a result, activities like debates, "thinking out loud," and active listening are their favored methods of learning (Haggart, 2013). Teaching phonics is often an effective strategy for instructing auditory learners, particularly novice readers (Dunn, 2016). Auditory learners typically use expressive voices during the learning process, and background white noise or soft music can help them stay focused (Freitas, 2016).

Auditory learners often have the ability to discern the true meaning of speech by interpreting auditory cues such as tone and pitch. For instance, they may repeat a phone number aloud and rely on its sound for recall. These learners excel in writing detailed responses to lectures they have attended and perform well in oral examinations by effectively processing and retaining verbally delivered information from lectures, speeches, and discussions.

Proponents of auditory learning emphasize that auditory/verbal learners often struggle to comprehend material through reading alone unless accompanied by background sounds. In such cases, auditory stimuli like music or ambient noise (e.g., television or conversations) can boost their productivity. For teachers, accommodating auditory learners in diverse classrooms presents a challenge, requiring strategies to ensure their needs are met while fostering collaborative learning among all learners.

Table 4 shows the kinesthetic learning style preference of the Grade IV learners.

Table 4. *Learning style preference of learners in terms of kinesthetic*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation	Interpretation
1. need frequent breaks when I work or study.	4.36	.856	A	Very True of Me
2. manipulates objects to help me to remember what someone says.	3.95	1.368	O	Generally True of Me
3. get nervous when I sit still too long.	3.43	1.489	O	Generally True of Me
4. plays with or bites on my pens during lectures.	3.40	1.546	O	Generally True of Me
5. think better when I move around. (e.g. pacing)	3.39	1.507	O	Generally True of Me
6. need to eat something when I read or study.	3.38	1.535	O	Generally True of Me
7. prefer standing to sitting, If I have to choose between sitting and standing.	3.37	1.440	O	Generally True of Me
8. prefers to start doing things rather than checking the directions first.	3.05	1.660	S	Moderately True of Me
9. draw lots of pictures (doodles) in my notebook during lectures.	3.00	1.627	S	Moderately True of Me
10. moves my hands when I speak.	2.82	1.571	S	Moderately True of Me
Overall	3.42	.874	O	Generally True of Me

Legend: 4.20-5.00 = Always (A) / Very true of me | 3.20-4.19 = Often (O) / Generally true of me | 2.60-3.19 = Sometimes (S) / Moderately true of me | 1.80-2.59 = Rarely (R) / Slightly true of me | 1.00-1.79 = Never (N) / Not at all true of me

As shown in Table 4, the statement "need frequent breaks when I work or study" has a mean of 4.36, $sd = .856$ was very true of the learners. The statements "manipulate objects to help me to remember what someone says" has a mean of 3.95, $sd = 1.368$, "get nervous when I sit still too long" has a mean of 3.43, $sd = 1.489$ and "play with or bite on my pens during lectures" has a mean of 3.40, $sd = 1.546$ were moderately true of the learners. Moreover, the statements "prefer to start doing things rather than checking the directions first" has a mean of 3.05, $sd = 1.660$, "draw lots of pictures (doodles) in my notebook during lectures" has a mean of 3.00, $sd = 1.627$ and "move my hands when I speak" has a mean of 2.82, $sd = 1.571$ were moderately true of them. Overall, the learning style preference of learners in terms of kinesthetic was generally true of the learners has a mean of 3.42, $sd = .874$ with a descriptive rating of often(O) and qualitative interpretation of Generally True of Me.

This indicates a preference for experiential learning and active participation. They seek to relocate and manipulate objects to facilitate their learning. Kinesthetic learners acquire knowledge most effectively by engaging their large or gross motor muscles (Keys Learning, 1993).

Kinesthetic learners get optimal success when actively participating in the learning experience. They assimilate knowledge more rapidly while engaged in a science laboratory, theatrical performance, play, field excursion, dance, or other dynamic activity. Due to the significant prevalence of kinesthetic learners, education is transitioning to a more experiential methodology; manipulatives and various "props" are integrated into nearly every academic discipline, ranging from physical education to language arts. Experiential teaching methods are increasingly acknowledged for their effectiveness in meeting the complex requirements of kinesthetic learners, alongside the varied needs of auditory and visual learners.

Table 5 shows the summary of the learning style preference of the Grade IV learners.

Table 5. Summary of the Learning Style Preference of Grade 4 Learners

Learning Style	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation	Interpretation
A. Visual Learning Style	3.90	.463	Often (O)	Generally True of Me
B. Auditory Learning Style	3.58	.874	Often (O)	Generally True of Me
C. Kinaesthetic Learning Style	3.42	.874	Often (O)	Generally True of Me
Grand Mean	3.63	0.737	Often (O)	Generally True of Me

Legend: 4.20-5.00 = Always (A) / Very true of me | 3.20-4.19 = Often (O) / Generally true of me | 2.60-3.19 = Sometimes (S) / Moderately true of me | 1.80-2.59 = Rarely (R) / Slightly true of me | 1.00-1.79 = Never (N) / Not at all true of me

Table 5 shows that the learning style preference of the Grade IV learners is Visual learning style with an overall mean of 3.90 and a standard deviation of 0.463. The majority of learners in Pangantucan North District are visual learners. Auditory learners are then followed by kinesthetic learners. This indicates that learners comprehend and acquire knowledge in diverse ways. They vary in their methods of absorbing, processing, comprehending, and retaining information. Teachers must comprehend the variations in their learners' learning styles to effectively use appropriate tactics and maintain optimal practices in their daily activities, curriculum, and assessments.

Level of Motivation of the Grade IV Learners

There are four variables that assess the motivation of Grade IV learners namely, Interest/Enjoyment, Perceived Competence, Effort/Importance, and Pressure/Tension.

Table 6 shows the level of motivation of the learners in terms of Interest in the Grade IV learners.

Table 6. Level of motivation of the learners in terms of Interest

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation	Interpretation
1. am thinking about how much I enjoyed it, While I am doing it,	4.15	1.102	Moderately Agree	Motivated
2. find learning something fun to do.	4.14	1.296	Moderately Agree	Motivated
3. would describe learning activity as very interesting.	4.03	1.311	Moderately Agree	Motivated
4. thought learning was quite enjoyable.	3.88	1.364	Moderately Agree	Motivated
5. enjoyed doing the learning activity very much.	3.87	1.469	Moderately Agree	Motivated
6. learning did not hold my attention at all.	3.21	1.512	Moderately Agree	Motivated
7. Never thought learning was a boring activity.	3.20	1.582	Moderately Agree	Motivated
Overall	3.78	.731	Moderately Agree	Motivated

Legend: Strongly Agree = Highly Motivated | Moderately Agree = Motivated | Agree = Moderately Motivated | Disagree = Less Motivated | Strongly Disagree = Not Motivated

All statements in Table 6 show that the learners were motivated. The statements “am thinking about how much I enjoyed it, While I am doing it” has a mean of 4.15, SD = 1.102, “find learning something fun to do” has a mean of 4.14, SD = 1.296, and “would describe learning activity as very interesting” has a mean of 4.03, SD = 1.311 were first three statements in terms of mean values. The statement “Never thought learning is a boring activity” has a mean of 3.20, SD = 1.582 got the lowest mean. Overall, the learners were motivated in terms of Interest has a mean of 3.78, SD = .731 with a descriptive rating of Moderately Agree and qualitative interpretation of Motivated.

The findings indicated that grade IV learners derived pleasure from the learning experience. The interests inherent in each human vary. Interest in an individual motivates engagement in their pursuits to attain objectives. Winkel, W.S. (2014) As per Hilgard (2013), the formula for interest is as follows: "Interest is a sustained inclination to focus on and derive enjoyment from specific activities or content. It involves a continual awareness and retention of certain pursuits, consistently accompanied by pleasure." Shah (2003) defines it as "the interest and the mean trend of high excitement or great desire for something."

Ideally, a child should possess an interest in a subject to facilitate genuine learning. The magnitude of interest significantly influences an individual's disposition towards the action undertaken. Likewise, regarding reading. For some individuals, reading is perceived as a pastime integrated into their regular activities. For learners, an interest in reading is essential for those anticipated to enhance the learning process. By fostering self-interest in reading, learners are likely to cultivate independence, hence facilitating optimal learning outcomes.

Table 7 shows the level of motivation of the learners in terms of perceived competence of the grade IV learners.

Table 7. Level of motivation of the learners in terms of perceived competence

Indicator	Melevelan	SD	Qualitative Interpretation	Interpretation
1. am satisfied with my performance task.	4.34	.980	Strongly Agree	Highly Motivated
2. think I am pretty good at learning.	4.17	1.287	Moderately Agree	Motivated
3. Could do very well in learning tasks.	3.91	1.209	Moderately Agree	Motivated
4. was pretty skilled at learning activities.	3.61	1.421	Moderately Agree	Motivated
5. felt pretty competent after working on a learning task for a while.	3.37	1.557	Moderately Agree	Motivated
6. think I did pretty well in a learning activity, compared to other learners.	3.21	1.432	Moderately Agree	Motivated
Overall	3.77	.732	Moderately Agree	Motivated

Legend: Strongly Agree = Highly Motivated | Moderately Agree = Motivated | Agree = Moderately Motivated | Disagree = Less Motivated | Strongly Disagree = Not Motivated

The statement “am satisfied with my performance task” has a mean of 4.34, sd = .980 showing highly motivated learners. Other statements in the table reveal motivated learners. The statement “think I did pretty well in a learning activity, compared to other learners” has a mean of 3.21, sd = 1.432 got the lowest mean. In general, the learners were moderately motivated in terms of Perceived Competence has a mean of 3.77 or .732 with a descriptive rating of Moderately Agree and a qualitative interpretation of Motivated.

The findings indicated that the grade IV learners exhibit self-confidence and demonstrate proficiency in both independent and collaborative learning. They are not juxtaposing themselves with other classmates. They are concentrating on their individual responsibilities and on the expectations about their academic success.

Perceived competence refers to an individual's self-assessment of their abilities and their capacity to influence their environment and circumstances. It is the degree to which an individual views their own talent and efficacy in a specific context. Individuals often select challenges commensurate with their talents. Enhancing perceived competence can be achieved by initiating with modest goals and tasks, progressively advancing to a level where the group or person excels. Rewards and commendations are essential for enhancing perceived competence, alongside constructive feedback.

Table 8 shows the level of motivation of the learners in terms of Effort/Importance of the Grade IV learners.

Table 8. Level of motivation of the learners in terms of effort

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation	Interpretation
1. put a lot of effort into learning.	4.47	1.015	Strongly Agree	Highly motivated
2. give importance to doing well at any learning task.	4.31	1.095	Strongly Agree	Highly motivated
3. tried very hard on learning activities.	4.27	1.047	Strongly Agree	Highly motivated
4. did not put much energy into learning.	3.47	1.500	Moderately Agree	Motivated
5. did not try very hard to do well in the learning activity.	3.36	1.608	Moderately Agree	Motivated
Overall	3.98	.651	Moderately Agree	Motivated

Legend: Strongly Agree = Highly Motivated | Moderately Agree = Motivated | Agree = Moderately Motivated | Disagree = Less Motivated | Strongly Disagree = Not Motivated

As shown in Table 8, the statements “put a lot of effort in learning” has a mean of 4.47, sd = 1.015, “give importance to doing well at any learning task” has a mean of 4.31, sd = 1.095, and “tried very hard on learning activity” has a mean of 4.27, sd = 1.047 show highly motivated learners. Two statements reveal that the learners were motivated. They were: “did not put much energy in learning” has a mean of 3.47, sd = 1.500 and “did not try very hard to do well in learning activity” has a mean of 3.36, sd = 1.608. Overall, the learners were motivated in terms of effort has a mean of 3.98, sd = .651 with the descriptive rating of Moderately Agree and qualitative interpretation of Motivated.

Table 8 indicates that the grade IV kids are exerting considerable effort in their learning, dedicating significant time and energy to the process. According to Bandura, A. (1986), motivation stems from an individual's self-efficacy toward a task. Bandura characterizes self-efficacy as the convictions we hold on our capabilities, which influence our decision-making, effort exertion, and perseverance under adversity. Bandura observes that mastery experience is one of the most potent sources of self-efficacy in the classroom.

Table 9. Level of motivation of the learners in terms of pressure

Mean	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation	Interpretation
1. was very relaxed in doing learning activities.	3.95	1.024	Moderately Agree	Motivated
2. did not feel nervous when asked to do something in school.	3.77	1.393	Moderately Agree	Motivated
3. felt very tense while doing learning activities.	3.49	1.335	Moderately Agree	Motivated
4. felt pressured while doing learning tasks.	3.45	1.334	Moderately Agree	Motivated
5. was anxious while working on learning tasks.	3.25	1.392	Moderately Agree	Motivated
Overall	3.58	.778	Moderately Agree	Motivated

Legend: Strongly Agree = Highly Motivated | Moderately Agree = Motivated | Agree = Moderately Motivated | Disagree = Less Motivated | Strongly Disagree = Not Motivated

Table 9 shows the level of motivation of the learners in terms of Pressure/Tension in Grade IV learners.

As revealed in Table 9, all statements show that the learners were motivated. The statement “was very relaxed in doing learning activities” has a mean of 3.95, $sd = 1.024$ got the highest mean. The statement “was anxious while working on learning tasks” has a mean of 3.25, $sd = 1.392$ got the lowest mean. Overall, the learners were motivated in terms of pressure having a mean of 3.58, $sd = .778$ with a descriptive rating of Moderately Agree and a qualitative interpretation of Motivated.

The findings indicate that fourth-grade learners I moderately agree with all evidence suggesting that they are motivated to learn and experienced pressure and anxiety during the learning process. Children are subjected to pressure to excel academically. Currently, it is frequently reported that youngsters experience pressure, suggesting that is a widespread societal issue. Teachers feel a sense of obligation to ensure that learners thrive, as they are responsible for their instruction. If the learners fail, they may perceive it as a personal failure in their role as teachers, leading parents to attribute the blame to them for inadequately instructing their children. Parents and teachers should exhibit greater empathy for the challenges faced by children in their literacy development. Teachers must exhibit sufficient flexibility in addressing the needs of various learners.

Table 10 shows the summary of the Level of Motivation of the Grade IV Learners.

Table 10. Summary of the Level of Motivation of the Grade IV Learners

Motivation	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation	Interpretation
A. Effort	3.98	.651	Moderately Agree	Motivated
B. Interest	3.78	.731	Moderately Agree	Motivated
C. Perceived Competence	3.77	.732	Moderately Agree	Motivated
D. Pressure/Tension	3.58	.778	Moderately Agree	Motivated
Grand Mean	3.78	.723	Moderately Agree	Motivated

Legend: Strongly Agree = Highly Motivated | Moderately Agree = Motivated | Agree = Moderately Motivated | Disagree = Less Motivated | Strongly Disagree = Not Motivated

Table 10 shows the Level of Motivation of the Grade VI Learners of which effort has the highest mean of 3.98, followed by interest with a mean of 3.78, perceived competence with a mean of 3.77, and last pressure/tension with a mean of 3.58. This indicates that the Grade IV learners moderately concur that the four motivators can and will inspire them to endeavor to accomplish various academic duties.

Academic Achievement of the Grade IV Learners in Araling Panlipunan

Table 11 presents the Academic Achievement of the Grade IV Learners for S.Y 2022-2023.

Table 11. Academic achievement of Grade IV learners

Grades	f	%	Description
90 and Above	0	0	Outstanding
85 – 89	40	29.2	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	69	50.4	Satisfactory
75 – 79	28	20.4	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and Below	0	0	Did not Meet Expectations
Mean = 82.53	SD = 3.85	Satisfactory	
Total	137	100.0	

Table 11 shows that the majority of the learners were satisfactory in their academic achievements in Araling Panlipunan with grades between 80 – 84 with a frequency of 69 or 50.4%. Some of them got grades between 85 – 90 with a frequency of 40 or 29.2%. There were learners whose grades were between 75 – 79 with a frequency of 28 or 20.4%. Their academic achievements were satisfactory with an average of 82.53.

This indicates that over fifty percent of grade IV learners exhibit satisfactory performance. Teachers must simply inspire learners to enhance their performance. Motivation and other good influences will undoubtedly enhance the learners' academic performance and achievement. Okita (2014) identifies two categories of characteristics that influence learners' academic success. There are (1) internal and (2) external classroom aspects that significantly influence learners' performance. Internal classroom factors encompass learners' proficiency in English, class timetables, class size, English textbooks, assessment outcomes, learning resources, homework assignments, classroom environment, complexity of course content, the teacher's role, utilized technology, and examination systems.

Relationship among Learners' academic achievement, motivation, and Learning Style

Table 12 presents the relationship among academic achievement, motivation, and learning style of learners.

Table 12 presents the relationship between the variables of learning style and motivation with academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan. The results show that for learning style, Visual learners had an f -value of 1.623 and a p -value of .088, Auditory learners had an f -value of .864 and a p -value of .593, and Kinesthetic learners had an f -value of 1.493 and a p -value of .129. These results indicate that there is no significant relationship between learning style and academic achievement.

Table 12. *Test of significant relationship among the academic achievement, motivation, and learning style of the learners*

		<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Visual	Between Groups	4.260	13	.328	1.623	.088
	Within Groups	24.840	123	.202		NS
	Total	29.100	136			
Auditory	Between Groups	8.616	13	.663	.864	.593
	Within Groups	94.395	123	.767		NS
	Total	103.010	136			
Kinesthetics	Between Groups	13.997	13	1.077	1.493	.129
	Within Groups	88.727	123	.721		NS
	Total	102.724	136			
Interest	Between Groups	6.197	13	.477	.881	.575
	Within Groups	66.569	123	.541		NS
	Total	72.766	136			
Competence	Between Groups	6.717	13	.517	.960	.494
	Within Groups	66.198	123	.538		NS
	Total	72.914	136			
Effort	Between Groups	4.997	13	.384	.899	.556
	Within Groups	52.608	123	.428		NS
	Total	57.605	136			
Pressure	Between Groups	9.712	13	.747	1.266	.243
	Within Groups	72.599	123	.590		NS
	Total	82.311	136			

* *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*** *Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Table 12 presents the relationship between the variables of learning style and motivation with academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan. The results show that for learning style, Visual learners had an f-value of 1.623 and a p-value of .088, Auditory learners had an f-value of .864 and a p-value of .593, and Kinesthetic learners had an f-value of 1.493 and a p-value of .129. These results indicate that there is no significant relationship between learning style and academic achievement.

In terms of motivation, the findings were as follows: Interest had an f-value of .881 and a p-value of .575, Perceived Competence had an f-value of .960 and a p-value of .494, Effort had an f-value of .899 and a p-value of .556, and Pressure had an r-value of 1.266 and a p-value of .243. These results suggest that motivation does not significantly affect the learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan.

Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that "There is no significant relationship between academic achievement, motivation, and learning style of the learners," is accepted.

Conclusions

Based on the data gathered in the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The preferred learning style of Grade IV learners is Visual, followed by Auditory and Kinesthetic. This indicates that the learners have diverse ways of understanding, learning, processing, and retaining information.

The Grade IV learners moderately agree with the indicators of the four motivators: effort, interest, perceived competence, and pressure. This suggests that these motivators have contributed to their satisfactory academic achievement and will continue to support their success in completing various tasks, which will aid in their future development.

The academic achievement level of Grade IV learners is satisfactory. This implies that the learners are capable of achieving success, and teachers should focus on motivating them to foster a passion for learning.

There is no significant relationship between learners' academic achievement, learning styles, and motivation. This suggests that academic achievement does not depend solely on learning style or motivation; other factors also influence the academic performance of learners.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are provided:

Given the diversity of Grade IV learners, with some being visual learners, others auditory, and some kinesthetic, it is recommended that teachers be trained in various teaching approaches and strategies to cater to learners with different learning styles. Teachers may be equipped with hands-on teaching techniques, particularly because of the significant number of kinesthetic learners, as well as the varying needs of auditory and visual learners.

Department of Education (DepEd) personnel, particularly school administrators and teachers, may implement various activities and reward systems to sustain the learners' motivation and encourage them to achieve very satisfactory academic performance. This will help learners appreciate the importance of learning and strive for excellence. Teachers may remain mindful of the learners' learning styles and other factors that may influence academic performance, ensuring they use diverse strategies and approaches in the teaching and learning process.

Since the academic achievement of Grade IV learners is satisfactory, it is strongly recommended that school heads, teachers, and parents collaborate to design programs, activities, and reward systems that inspire learners to excel academically. Teachers may also incorporate immersion techniques alongside direct instruction to encourage learners to recognize the value of in-depth learning.

Finally, it is recommended that further research be conducted to verify whether the findings of this study hold true in other contexts, as some previous studies have contradicted the results of this research.

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